

Sustain Sahel

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Deliverable 8.5 Project logo, artwork, design and user manuals

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I. Executive Summary

D8.5 records the process adopted to create SustainSahel's logo, a vital emblem that will help cement and promote the project's vision and ambition to improve the farming livelihoods of those dwelling in the Sahel. Associated with the development of the logo, D8.5 also documents the choice of the colour palette and the range of visual material required to present and explain the scope of the project. As clearly stated in the proposal, due and consistent attention is being paid in the design and artwork elements of the project to diversity and inclusion of female and youth voices to ensure the project reflects the involvement of, and contribution to the programme of work, of all stakeholders.

Section 3 of D8.5 provides information, direction, and advice to all partners regarding the use of the key elements created and available to support communications and dissemination activities to drive engagement and eventual impact. This part of D8.5 will be produced as a separate working document for all partners to access on the SharePoint as a ready reference as to how the logo, for example, should be used. This Section also sets out the key obligations of partners to support the communications & dissemination efforts, particularly in regard to the identification and submission of content for the website, social media, and e-news for which editorial schedules will be created.

Section 4 Project Materials and the Appendix lay out clearly for all partners the collateral that is currently available, items that are promised and in development, plus the items that will become available as the project progresses. During the project's lifetime, the range and style of materials available to support partners' work will be reviewed and assessed, with new needs/ideas addressed as budget allows. Particular attention will always be paid to creating materials in English and French and in other local languages if and as the need arises.

2. Project Logo

2.1 Initial Ideas and Design Specifications

To initiate the design of the project logo, Minerva held a discussion session with WP8 partners and the coordinating team to identify a specific list of criteria for the logo design. Following this, initial logo concept designs were created in the form of a logo design briefing document. This document contained background information about the project and a wide range of visual elements directly relevant to the project's actions, geography, and scope, as well as the specific criteria for the design as identified in the discussion.

The specific criteria agreed following discussion were:

- Simplicity in design
- Typography preferred over graphic
- Green and brown tones best represent the colours of the Sahel region
- Visual graphic representation of the Sahel region

Typography

With a typographic style of logo preferred over an image or graphic based logo, it was important to select an appropriate font that best represented the project in terms of 'look and feel'. After identifying an assortment of fonts in various styles, a selection of six were identified as suitable. These fonts included softer cursive styles, and blockier, bolder styles.

Colour

An inspirational colour palette was created by gathering a range of images focusing on the Sahel region landscape and picking dominant colours, resulting in a palette of earthy, rich colours ranging from deep browns to bright greens. Referring back to the criteria, this palette was then filtered down to a selection of 12 key colours (as shown in Fig 1 below).

Fig 1 – Colour Palette:

Visual representation of Sahel region

To visually represent the Sahel region within the logo, a small graphic or visual ‘element’ could be incorporated. To decide what this ‘element’ could be, an assortment of graphics relevant to the project were identified, including imagery of shrubs and crops, small farming animals common in Sahel region, and a map of the Sahel region identified across the African countries.

Initial Designs

Using the elements of colour, typography, and visual representation, three logo design concepts were created. These designs were shared with Wp8 and coordinating team members for feedback.

Design Concept 1:

A long and slim typographic logo including a black un-joined cursive style font over a brown-to-green gradient to represent the colours of the Sahel. This concept contains two different visual representations of the Sahel region; the top logo shows a small shrub at the right-hand side of the logo, whilst the lower logo shows a ghost-underlay image of the Sahel region.

DESIGN CONCEPT 1

Design Concept 2:

Similar to concept 1, concept 2 is a long and slim typographic logo, using two varied fonts, the top logo font is a joined cursive, and the bottom logo font is the same as in concept 1. Each font is over a three-colour brown-to-yellow-to-green gradient. This concept contains two different visual representations of the Sahel region; the top logo shows a small shrub at the right-hand side of the logo, whilst the lower logo shows a mid-ground ghost image of the Sahel region.

Design Concept 3:

This logo utilised a bolder, capitalised font style in a three-colour brown-to-yellow-to-green gradient font colour. This font is laid over a background image of the Sahel region.

2.2 Design Development

Following feedback from WP8 partners and coordinating team, the three logo design concepts were developed further into two, focusing on concept designs 2 and 3. Feedback included:

Concept 2 development

- Make the black text stand out more against the background
- Use the less cursive font
- Lighten the darker brown in the gradient
- Include the Sahel map in the icon logo

Concept 3 development

- Change colour of the Sahel shading in background map

Developed Designs

Design 1:

Design one is a typographic logo with a gradient background. The colours used highlight the most prominent colours found across the Sahel region; red, brown, yellow and green. Using the colours in a gradient rather than choosing one solid is not only practical as it means a wider range of colours can be used in project branding, but also portrays the scope of the project and the different regions and countries across the Sahel. To avoid harsh edges to the logo, a brush style effect has been used. This gives the logo more emphasis and avoids a box-like look on a page. The text is a simple but elegant font with a sweeping brush feel. The font is easy to read and bold enough to stand out against the gradient background.

Below are examples of how this logo can be altered into a logo icon to suit across social channels and on document, as well as examples of how the logo could appear on different backgrounds.

LOGO ICON

INVERSIONS

Design 2:

Design two is a typographic logo with a gradient font and a map background. The font is strong and bold, drawing attention to the logo and ensuring it stands out across all platforms and media usage. As with design one, the colours used highlight the most prominent colours found across the Sahel region; red, brown, yellow and green. The logo incorporates a map of Africa, highlighting the Sahel region and the project's area of focus.

Below are examples of how this logo can be converted into a logo icon to suit many social channels and on documents, as well as examples of how the logo appears on different backgrounds.

LOGO ICON

INVERSIONS

These two designs were circulated to all partners who were asked to vote by doodle poll for one design or the other. Voting was blind so all could vote for their own preferred logo without seeing other votes. Logo Design I was overwhelmingly voted the favourite and confirmed as the project logo.

2.3 Final Logo and Icon Design

Project final logo:

Project final logo icon:

2.4 Use of logo

It was important to have the logo designed and finalised in the first months of the project to enable its use across the website (www.sustainsahel.net) and on the project social media channels (twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube). The logo and icon, and their inversions, have been made available to all partners to download and use as appropriate via the project's SharePoint repository.

3. User Manual – Guidance for Partners on Utilising Artwork & Design

This section explains how the artwork and designs created for the SustainSahel project should be used across all documents and media both online and in print.

3.1 Correct Use of Logo

The SustainSahel logo is available in various formats for partners on the SharePoint repository.

The main SustainSahel logo, or the smaller SustainSahel logo icon, must be present on all internal and external project documents and on all promotional materials, as well as prominently displayed on all online and social channels. Templates for many documents have already been created with the logo embedded in appropriate locations (see next section) and all social media channels have the logo icon as their profile image.

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On white and light-coloured backgrounds, the full colour logos can be used. It is advised that, where possible, PNG files of the logo with transparent backgrounds be used.

On dark coloured backgrounds, a version of the logo with white text has been created to ensure the logo can still be read clearly.

The logo and icon may be enlarged or reduced in size but must always be presented in the correct size format, and never distorted in proportions. See examples below:

Correct size formatting

Incorrect proportions in size formatting

3.2 Project Colours and Use

The gradient of brown-yellow-green in the project logo allows a wide range of colours to be used in project materials whilst keeping in line with the colour palette of the project. A set of key project logo colours have been identified and each hex colour code specified. All partners have access to these colours

and their colour codes on the project's SharePoint. These colours are to be used by all partners for all materials developed to create synergy across project documents and materials, building the project's 'brand'.

A set of complementary colours have also been identified to use in project materials. This set of colours is particularly useful for Wp8 communication and dissemination activities where promotional materials will be created and where the use of darker tones may be more appropriate. This set of complementary colours also includes green #70ad47 which is a standard green within Microsoft platforms and is easily accessible to all partners to use in reporting etc. For example, it has been used in this document for the heading text.

LOGO COLOURS

COMPLEMENTARY COLOURS

Each of the Field Sites, once confirmed, could be colour-coded to enable easier identification of the information online (e.g. on website and in social media posts) and in physical documents. These colours can then be utilised across the website and social media posts as well as in promotional. To be discussed with the Wp and site teams when appropriate.

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3.3 Website

The initial website technical structure and aesthetics have been designed and developed by FiBL and Minerva with the look and feel of the site being driven by the project logo and colours. Consideration will be given throughout to represent diversity and inclusion with particular attention to content and imagery of women and youth, vital groups with which the project must engage.

Imagery on the site depicts a range of landscape and farming scenes from the Sahel region, with the goal being to incorporate many more ‘on the ground’ images and photographs taken by the project team in Africa in a gallery and on various sections on the website.

Structurally, the website includes background, project overview, specific information about each of the work packages, project partners, and contact information. The initial website is currently undergoing further development and will be under review continuously. An editorial schedule is being created to support the contribution of content from all partners and to ensure the website stays up-to-date and engaging, supporting efforts to widen the project’s reputation and influence content as the project develops.

In addition to project information, pages will cater for the interests of different stakeholders from the wider public to policy-players at national, European, and international levels, to farmers and their advisers to actors across the appropriate agricultural value chains. Tailored and relevant content will be provided relevant for each group, as well as give ‘colour’ to the website. An overview and history of the Sahel region with insights provided as to the needs of the area, as well as the purpose and expected outcomes from the project’s work. Project partners are already equipped with the knowledge necessary for creating this page and will be asked to provide information and appropriate imagery to saturate this page.

As the project progresses, pages will be created dedicated to each of the field sites capturing and presenting the nature and needs of the area, as well as the work to be conducted. ‘Voices from the field’ plus photos, videos and podcasts will be secured and presented, as well as technical information about the specific methods being implemented. Partners from each field site will be closely involved in the development and maintenance of these pages.

An events page will highlight not only the project’s own events, but also external events and initiatives related to the project’s objectives and ambition being organised by associated projects and organisations.

3.4 Social Media

Social media accounts for the project have been set up on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube, with each channel branded using the logo icon and relevant project imagery. The project social channels will be highly aesthetic and utilise the project colours and imagery to their full extent. Graphics, videos, podcasts images, and photos will populate the channels created with symmetry to ensure the look and feel of the project is well represented across all social content.

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The requirement to engage with youth and women farmers will be given appropriate priority.

Partners will be actively involved in preparing and delivering content for social media from the field sites will be asked to provide 'voices from the field', all partners will be involved in providing project updates at various stages throughout the funded period as well as more specific information about each partner organisation and more personal stories about the individuals involved.

3.5 E-news

A project e-news will be created and disseminated to project partners and wider stakeholders at regulated intervals throughout the funded period. The e-news content will cover updates from the project and forward information on events and initiatives to secure ongoing interest and engagement. The aesthetic design of the e-news will be driven by the project logo and colours and available content. External recipients will have signed up via the website and given explicit permission for retention of minimal personal information on a GDPR compliant database.

3.6 Templates

A variety of document templates have been designed and made available to partners on the SharePoint project repository to build up the identity and brand of the project. New templates will be created as required and edited throughout as required.

i. Deliverable front page & prelims

A front page and layout for deliverable documents has been designed by FiBL and made available to all project partners. This template ensures each document contains all the required technical information necessary for EC deliverables.

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ii. Email footer with working links (PDF only)

An email footer including the main project logo and information about the website and social channels has been created. This email footer is available in PDF format with working links as well as PNG format which does not have working links. Partners will be advised to use this footer along with their own contact and organisation information in all email communications regarding the project's activities.

iii. PowerPoint presentation

A PowerPoint presentation master slide design document has been created and disseminated to all partners. The design includes a title slide with the logo and a content slide with the logo icon. All slides contain the project number and EC funding recognition. This slide design has already been used by the project at the kick-off meeting held in MI. Space is allowed for the inclusion of each partner's logo.

iv. Social Posts

Suites of social post templates are being created to suit each social platform and will continue to be created across the life of the project. These templates will use the project colours to create synergy across all channels and present the project logo or icon in a suitable position. Each social template will be tailored to the content where necessary. Future templates will also remain true to the design and colours of the project branding.

Content for social posts will be provided by all partners through a number of means: event information, project updates, partner updates, information about partner organisations, personal stories from individuals involved in the project, views from the field sites, photographs and videos, relevant information from external related sources, etc.

v. Flyer (generic & adaptable versions)

A generic flyer for the project will be created using the logo and project information. Contact information and links to the website and social channels will be prominently displayed on the promotional flyer. This flyer will be available in English and French and be made available to partners to print locally. A second flyer template will be created with blank areas instead of text where partners can input further local information, and also translated where necessary and appropriate.

vi. Press Release

A generic press release template for main communication releases from the SustainSahel project will be created and utilised by WVP8 for all SustainSahel press releases. A word/PDF document template will follow the same design structure as other project documents. Press releases sent out using the My News Desk platform will have an adapted design structure due to the formatting of the release via the platform, this design will contain the project logo and relevant contact information and EC recognition information.

An adjusted template of each central release created will be provided for partners and organisations to add in their own information and to reflect ‘the local’ situation as appropriate and to be issued locally in the appropriate language.

3.7 Photos and Images

Photos and images of the Sahel region and local farming practices have started to be collected from external online sources and from partners. These images reflect the colour and diversity of the landscape, as well as local farming methods, and were integral to the creation of the project logo and colour palette. Particular attention will be paid to diversity and inclusion.

Partners have been asked to contribute photographs they have of the Sahel region to a gallery on the SharePoint repository along with an appropriate caption with a title and description. A public gallery of

photos will be made available to view on the website. Photos provided by partners will also be used across communication materials created by the project and on the website and social media channels (with appropriate permissions and clearance from the photographers). Photos cleared for use in the public domain by the media will also be made available on the Media corner of the website.

4. Project Materials

Core materials will be designed and delivered in both English and French where appropriate and feasible. Templated materials will also be produced enabling partners from all countries involved to adapt materials to highlight local scenarios and situation and produce in local languages. The needs, perceptions of and engagement with women and youth will be captured and represented across all materials produced and cascaded.

4.1 Currently Available and in Use

Many project materials and channels are already developed, made available to partners and in use. These include:

- Logo and icon
- Website
- Social channels
 - a) Facebook
 - b) Twitter
 - c) Instagram
 - d) YouTube
- PowerPoint Presentation master side
- Deliverable front page

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- Email footer
- Initial imagery and photos

4.2 To Be Available in the Future

Further project materials and templates are in development and will be made available to the consortium in the coming months as activity increases and needs arise. The planned materials are as follows:

- Social Media templates
- Press Release templates
- Project flyer and templates for adaptation & translation
- Briefing document template for range of stakeholders
- Post card 'leave behind'

As the project progresses with more opportunities for travel and engagement (post Covid-19 emergency) and more information, data and content becomes available, more ambitious outreach collateral will be produced, to include:

- Infographics to highlight the ambition and key aspects of the project
- Short videos from project partners and stakeholders in the field
- Podcasts
- Pull up poster banners for use at major events
- Conference materials as required to support the project's and partners attendance

WP8 will endeavour to respond to all demands and requests from partners for materials and content that support engagement activities. WP8 will, however, rely on the 'supply' side of the equation and require core content from partners, harvested from their day to day activities for the project.

5. Appendix

Templates

PDFs of Templates available at time of submission of the deliverable

All Templates for use by partners are uploaded to and available for download and use from SharePoint. The number of Templates available will increase over time with the ongoing needs of partners kept under review. Templates themselves will be reviewed regularly and adapted as required for use by all project partners.

I - Logo and icon

Versions for partner use are available on the SustainSahel internal communication platform in PNG format.

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2 - PowerPoint Presentation master side

Available on the SustainSahel internal communication platform.

3 - Deliverable front page

Available on the SustainSahel internal communication platform

4 - Email footer

Available on the SustainSahel internal communication platform

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PDFs of Draft Templates in progress at time of submission the oft he deliverable

5 - Social Media templates - drafts

6 - Press Release templates - draft

SustainSahel - PRESS RELEASE 00 ISSUED 00 MONTH 2020

PRESS RELEASE 00 - ISSUED 00 MONTH 2020

EMBARGOED UNTIL 00:01 00 MONTH 2020

Title of Press Release

Content

Ends/ Notes follow

Notes to Editors:

1. Further information regarding the project including requests for interviews with the project team and/or audio-visual content (photos/videos) please contact Rhonda Smith & Marie Saville in the UK at sustaincahel@minerva-comms.net - +44 (0) 1264 326427
2. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 sustainable food security programme. Project No: 861974 under call H2020-SFS-2019-2

SustainSahel PRESS RELEASE 00 - (DATE)

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WWW.SUSTAINSAHEL.NET

7 - Post card 'leave behind'

The overall objective of SustainSAHEL is to enhance the resilience and intensification potential of smallholder agricultural farming systems to climate change through scalable innovations on crop-shrub-livestock (CSL) integration.

SustainSAHEL aims to develop CSL systems through innovation platforms (IPs) in order to improve productivity and farmers' income. We will assess adoption and scaling potential of improved CSL integration, while simultaneously optimizing proven technologies, improving herder-farmer cooperation, tackling socioeconomic constraints for adoption and contributing to local economic revival.

Our approach is embedded within the production systems of agro-ecology and organic agriculture, while comprising elements of conservation agriculture. Investigations on CSL, as well as soil quality and hydrology will be conducted through on-station and on-farm experiments and demonstration plots. We will identify drought resistant shrub teams that are in synchrony with livestock requirements, and reduced tillage options that enhances the soil water capture and holding capacity. At the regional level, landscape modelling scenarios will analyse the promoted systems' resilience to climate change in West Africa.

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